

Uses of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy Technique in Pharmaceutical Analysis: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) is a physical phenomenon in which nuclei in a magnetic field absorb and re-emit electromagnetic radiation. Many scientific techniques exploit NMR phenomena to study molecular physics, crystals, and non-crystalline materials through nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy. NMR phenomena are also utilized in low-field NMR, NMR spectroscopy and MRI in the Earth's magnetic field (referred to as Earth's field NMR), and in several types of magnetometers. Modern NMR spectroscopy has been emphasizing the application in biomolecular systems and plays an important role in structural biology. NMR spectroscopy is very important to identify a drug or an excipient, evaluate the level of impurities (and to elucidate the structure), observe the course of a decomposition, to evaluate residual solvents, determine the isomeric composition, i.e. the ratio of diastereomers and the enantiomeric excess by means of chiral additive, assess a single drug or drug composition, characterize a polymer mostly being a mixture and used as excipients, identify counter ions (if of organic origin and having protons), characterize an entire formulation, e.g. a tablet. Fundamentals of quantitative NMR spectroscopy NMR spectroscopy can be considered as a primary ratio method of measurement being characterized by the fact that the ratio of substances can be determined directly from the physical context of the measurement without referencing to another substance. NMR has become one of the most powerful and versatile spectroscopic techniques for the analysis of biomacromolecules, allowing characterization of biomacromolecules and their complexes up to 100 kDa. Together with X-ray crystallography.

Keyword: Nuclear magnetic resonance, spectroscopy, Application, Metabolite analysis, Chemical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

NMR spectroscopy is known to be not very sensitive. However, for quality assessment of an API the sensitivity is sufficient as long as the signals considered are separated¹⁻³. The sensitivity has been enhanced in the past years by the development of high-field spectrometers (>400 MHz) for routine purposes, invention of gradient shimming techniques, and inverse or cryo probes as well as the microcoil technology. There are innumerable examples reported where the structure of an impurity, being normally not present in a drug, is elucidated by means of NMR spectroscopy. Even though NMR spectroscopy is a powerful tool for quality control it is rarely used in international pharmacopoeias⁴⁻⁶. Nevertheless, the pharmaceutical industries, especially "big pharma", started to use NMR spectra more often in routine quality analysis. However, it will take quite some time till q NMR spectroscopy will find its way into the monographs of the international pharmacopoeias. Moreover, a large market has developed for herbal medicines (HMs) as a safe alternative to synthetic PDE-5 inhibitors. Indeed, in contrast to conventional pharmaceuticals, HM are regarded by many as being harmless and free from any side-effects because of their

natural origin. However, their adulteration with conventional drugs is a growing trend and poses a health threat to patients who unwittingly consume a synthetic drug⁷⁻¹¹. HM marketed for enhancement of sexual function are the most affected. NMR spectroscopy is one of the two leading technologies for the structure determination of biomacromolecules at atomic resolution¹².

Applications of NMR spectroscopy are listed below

Solution structure

The only method for atomic-resolution structure determination of biomacromolecules in aqueous solutions under near physiological conditions or membrane mimetic environments. Structure determination by NMR is an established technique and is routinely used to determine three-dimensional structures of biological macromolecules in solution with molecular weights up to 30 kDa¹³⁻²¹. The power of NMR over other spectroscopic techniques results from the fact that every NMR active nucleus gives rise to an individual signal (resonance line) in the spectrum that can be resolved by multi-dimensional NMR techniques²²⁻²⁹. NMR spectra of biological macromolecules contain hundreds or even thousands of resonance lines which cannot be resolved in a

conventional one-dimensional (1D) NMR experiment. However, for a detailed analysis resolved lines are a prerequisite. Further, the interpretation of NMR data requires correlations between different nuclei which are implicitly contained in 1D spectra but often difficult to extract³⁰⁻³⁶. Large molecules tumble slower which results in faster relaxation and consequently broader lines in the NMR spectrum. Thus, the corresponding spectra show poor resolution and sensitivity. In practice, it becomes very hard to determine structures from proteins that have molecular weights above 40 kDa³⁷.

Molecular dynamics

The most powerful technique for quantifying motional properties of biomacromolecules³⁸.

Protein folding

The most powerful tool for determining the residual structures of unfolded proteins and the structures of folding intermediates. An efficient structure determination by NMR requires a highly purified protein preparation. An inhomogeneous preparation and/or aggregation of the protein as well as low molecular weight protonated impurities may severely impair the structure determination. The first step in every protein NMR study therefore involves optimization of the measurement conditions³⁹⁻⁴⁶. The pH, ionic strength, and temperature can often be adjusted to mimic physiological conditions. The macromolecule under study should be stable in the chosen conditions for many weeks. Any buffers, co-solvents and additives (e.g. detergent molecules) used should be hydrogen-free or deuterated⁴⁷.

Ionization state

The most powerful tool for determining the chemical properties of functional groups in biomacromolecules, such as the ionization states of ionizable groups at the active sites of enzymes. Weak intermolecular interactions allowing weak functional interactions between macrobiomolecules (e.g., those with dissociation constants in the micromolar to millimolar range) to be studied, which is not possible with other technologies⁴⁹.

Protein hydration

A power tool for the detection of interior water and its interaction with biomacromolecules⁵⁰.

Hydrogen bonding

A unique technique for the DIRECT detection of hydrogen bonding interactions.

Drug screening and design

Particularly useful for identifying drug leads and determining the conformations of the compounds bound to enzymes, receptors, and other proteins. Pharmaceutical and academic nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) groups have implemented NMR screening techniques as a powerful approach to identify and to investigate protein/ligand interactions. Pharmaceutical groups in particular have incorporated NMR screening strategies into their drug discovery and drug design programs⁵¹⁻⁵⁸. This stems from the fact that NMR screening is naturally synergistic with combinatorial or medicinal chemistry, high throughput screening (HTS), structure-based drug design, and genomics. Once the drug target is characterized, initial hits have to be found. Several NMR

techniques are applicable for this purpose; some of them can be performed in a high-throughput manner. For a detailed discussion of the techniques, the reader is referred elsewhere. In this paragraph, only the basis of NMR screening is described⁵⁹⁻⁶³. The effects resulting from the binding of a ligand to a protein can be divided into two classes: global and local effects. The former are size-dependent and therefore are suited to the observation on the ligand, while the latter are restricted to the binding region and can be monitored on both the target and the ligand. Upon binding to a macromolecule, the apparent molecular weight and hydrodynamic radius of a small ligand change dramatically by several orders of magnitude. Those changes can be detected with several different NMR experiments⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶. Relaxation filtering and diffusion editing reveal binding, but cannot provide any structural information. In contrast, NOE-based methods (NOE pumping, reverse NOE pumping) or STD not only prove interactions, in addition they can be used to characterize the binding epitope of the ligand⁶⁷.

Native membrane protein

Solid state NMR has the potential for determining atomic-resolution structures of domains of membrane proteins in their native membrane environments, including those with bound ligands.

Metabolite analysis

A very powerful technology for metabolite analysis. Metabonomics is defined as 'the quantitative measurement of the multiparametric metabolic response of living systems to pathophysiological stimuli or genetic modification' and is concerned with the study of the metabolic response of organisms to disease, environmental change or genetic modification⁶⁸. Metabonomics has many areas of application including biology and medicine with new developments such as pharmacometabonomics (the ability to predict drug responses prior to drug dosing) and the more general area of predictive metabonomics, emerging recently. Generally, the metabolic profile of a biological fluid is stable over a significant period of time at room temperature, and certainly stable enough for the acquisition of routine 1D and 2D 1HNMR data. However, there are exceptions. Some biological fluids are inherently unstable. A good example of this is human seminal fluid, where, post-ejaculation, enzymatic reactions take place that cause the biochemical transformation of some metabolites^{69,70}. In addition, if a sample such as animal urine, has been in contact with animal faeces at any stage, it will be microbiologically contaminated and potentially unstable. Bacterial growth in a urine sample, for instance, will result in the transformation of certain metabolites into new products, as the bacteria scavenge the biofluid for fuel sources.

Chemical analysis

A matured technique for chemical identification and conformational analysis of chemicals whether synthetic or natural. Material science a powerful tool in the research of polymer chemistry and physics. Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) is one of the most powerful tools in biology, chemistry, physics and medicine for the

investigation of structure, morphology and dynamics of various classes of compounds. Few analytical techniques in science match, in either breadth or depth, the impact achieved by nuclear magnetic resonance⁷¹. Polymer characterisation by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR) provides detailed structural information for product development and quality control considerations (QC). Expert evaluation of polymers by specialist techniques is essential in order to ensure product integrity and for quality control demands. One of the challenges polymer scientists face is molecular weight (average chain length) determination of their materials. While membrane osmometry, gel permeation chromatography, viscosity analysis and mass spectrometry are typically used for molecular weight determination, the techniques can be time consuming, inaccurate for the molecular weight ranges involved, or require specialized instrumentation. End-group analysis by NMR offers an easy alternative method using an instrument commonly found in many analytical labs. In addition, NMR analysis can also be used to accurately determine monomer ratios for various copolymer⁷².

CONCLUSION

NMR allows the observation of specific quantum mechanical magnetic properties of the atomic nucleus. The absolute amount of substances can be determined by using simple reference substances, which holds also true for coulometry, gravimetry or titrimetry. NMR is also routinely used in advanced medical imaging techniques, such as in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). A key feature of NMR is that the resonance frequency of a particular substance is directly proportional to the strength of the applied magnetic field. NMR has become a sophisticated and powerful analytical technology that has found a variety of applications in many disciplines of scientific research, medicine, and various industries. In addition, NMR provides unique and important molecular motional and interaction profiles containing pivotal information on protein function.

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